

An example for metrics assisted modeling of database performance

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ABSTRACT

Predicting performance of a database with a specified configuration under a certain workload is a very attractive idea – a good database model can help to find an optimal configuration, significantly reducing costs of benchmarking and experimentation. Yet it is hard to build a model that will be precise enough to provide practical insights. The major obstacle is complexity: even the simplest real-world database is a complicated non-linear system, with large number of subsystems and configurations knobs that impact performance and affect each other, produce feedback loops and unexpected dependencies.

In this work we demonstrate few examples of PostgreSQL specific "small" database models, which help explain narrow range of benchmark results. Such constructs are called "models" in a broad sense, because they include actual mathematical models, as well as simulations and simple data analysis. Important features of such models are: clear and limited application area; opportunistic use of monitoring and tracing techniques like PostgreSQL information views and dynamic userspace tracing on Linux.

We show, that despite "smallness" and limited area of application, such models are useful in predicting database performance, and could serve as building stones for larger and more comprehensive models.

1 INTRODUCTION

Predicting real-world database performance under certain specified conditions, without needing to run a benchmark, is a dream of anyone providing database services. Benchmarks require resources (e.g. money you have to spend on a cloud infrastructure), they are sometimes prohibitively expensive (e.g. generating enough data points, when a single benchmark run takes many days, may require enormous amount of time), and notoriously easy to get wrong. Yet it's important to be able to answer questions like would this database still satisfy its SLA if the configuration is modified? Or how much more resources are needed to be provisioned to handle increased workload?

There is plenty of research about predicting database performance. Many of them consider performance holistically, i.e. an entire database instance and its response to a specified type of workloads is modeled. One particularly popular example nowadays is to use machine learning models to find an optimal database configuration [14], [15]. Often some more manageable databases like RockDB are chosen as targets [11], instead of ubiquitous but complicated options like PostgreSQL. On the other side of spectrum there are researches that deal with cost modeling [13], which model much smaller part of the database abstracted to the essentials.

In this work we try to contribute few examples of database specific "smaller" models, which are designed to give a mechanistic explanation to observed performance. They are less general that

regular models, could be applied only under certain limited conditions and describe only a part of the overall performance picture, e.g. only I/O produced by an index maintenance. While similar to the cost modeling, "smaller" models do not abstract away specific database details. In fact, they could be developed and calibrated using monitoring and tracing, which allows managing complexity even if applied to databases like PostgreSQL and still get realistic results.

The first example is an I/O model of a B-Tree index under uniformly distributed read-only or insert-only workload. The model is compared against the experimental data. We use dynamic tracing with **perf** [3] for two purposes: to identify which effects to include or exclude from the model, and to calibrate the model.

The next example is latency simulation of a database query updating a column with a B-Tree index. The simulation gives an insight about how variance of various execution steps impact the final latency. We use dynamic tracing with **bpfftrace** [7] to calibrate simulation and then compare with real numbers.

The last example is simple data analysis for number of dead tuples in a B-Tree index. The analysis shows how same oscillation patterns appear at both page and index level. We use PostgreSQL extensions **pgstattuple** and **pageinspect** to get information about dead tuples directly from the database.

2 MODELING B-TREE I/O PROFILE

There are several performance metrics that could be measured for a B-Tree, each features different modeling complexity and importance for the overall performance profile. For example latency of searching one record in a B-Tree is valuable for CPU-bounded workloads, but depends on large number of complex factors (e.g. hardware configuration, memory access pattern, locking, etc) what often makes it hard to model. On the other hand the number of I/O operations triggered while searching for one record in a B-Tree is as valuable for I/O-bounded workloads, but involves fewer dependencies. Thus, we settled on the latter as the property to model, where under an I/O operation we understand an I/O request to the filesystem, not the actual I/O that hits the disk.

2.1 Formalization and limitations

B-Tree is a balanced tree data structure optimized for paged environment, where each node occupies a page, and to access an individual records a buffer pool in byte-addressable storage is required [9]. In PostgreSQL each level of the tree is a doubly-linked list of pages. New leaf pages are added to a B-Tree index when an existing leaf page cannot fit an incoming tuple. A page split operation makes room for items that originally belonged on the overflowing page by moving a portion of the items to a new page [6].

Reading or writing into a B-tree produces I/O operation depending on implementation of both the B-Tree access method and the

buffer pool. To understand how I/O is produced we could inspect the implementation of the buffer manager and B-Tree access method and deduce the I/O model. But due to active development it is easy to miss some important details, e.g. as we will see the SLRU is one source of I/O operation, yet it was recently reworked [10]. More holistic approach would be to benefit from tracing: prepare a test database environment with an expected workload, attach to the system tracepoints representing various filesystem I/O activity, and sample tracepoint hits during the benchmark.

Since PostgreSQL uses buffered I/O, it is important to distinguish what kind of information we would get in this way: a tracepoint may represent an operation on a filesystem cache (e.g. syscalls *pwrite*, *pread*, *fdatsync*, *fallocate*, or filesystem related tracepoints, etc), or a real block I/O that hits the storage (e.g. tracepoints from the *block:** group). To simplify the model and ignore filesystem cache effects, we will use only the former type of tracepoints for now.

```
$ perf record -e ext4:*
    --call-graph=dwarf -g -p <PIDs>
```

Using this approach we sample set of stacktraces pointing to the actual components of PostgreSQL that produce I/O during the expected workload. More about consequences of that is described in the conclusions section.

To further reduce complexity, we assume that the PostgreSQL database explicitly configured to produce as few as possible not relevant I/O operations. This means we try to reduce I/O noise as much as possible by e.g. configuring checkpointing, background writer, autovacuum, etc. Precise details about the configuration and its meaning could be found in the Appendix.

After all simplifications we identify following types of I/O for a B-Tree:

- Read a buffer from the disk if it was not found in the buffer cache
- Write a new zeroed buffer to extend a relation
- Write and sync WAL
- Write an SLRU page to extend SUBTRANS

To limit the scope we are going to consider only non-empty read-only (point read of an existing record) and insert-only (one record at the time) workloads. To reduce the modeling scope even further, we will consider only major contributing factors and ignore those types of I/O that happen infrequently (e.g. SLRU writes generate less than a percent of I/O in comparison with other groups). Another important simplification is that queries follow uniform distribution pattern, with equal probability of hitting any B-Tree page.

2.2 Model

2.2.1 Inputs. Having a formalized description of how a simplified B-Tree works, here are the inputs of our model:

- Q – total number of queries, executed against the database for the specified workload. This is going to be the main driving force producing a stream of I/O operations.
- Q_w – total number of write queries, executed against the database. Included into Q .
- I – average number of records per page. This input serves as an approximate description of the data schema we work

with, and helps to make the transformation step from isolated records to memory pages.

Following variables depend on the database configuration:

- M – size of the database buffer cache in pages. Corresponds to the *shared_buffers* settings in PostgreSQL and serves as a threshold between in-memory vs on-disk operations.
- $W_g(Q_w)$ – WAL grouping function, which tells how many WAL records are merged together before syncing to the storage.

Now lets figure out how different types of I/O depend on those inputs.

2.2.2 Read-only workload. As mentioned before, we consider only workload that consists of uniform point read queries, i.e. reading one value from the index at the time with equal probability to read any single index record. In this case a query might produce an I/O operations only if buffers, that have to be read while descending the tree, are not present in the buffer cache and have to be read from the disk. Intuitively it is clear that the probability of a buffer not being loaded in the buffer cache is reciprocal to the demand for other buffers – if lots of different buffers are loaded into the cache, most likely the one needed for the current query is already evicted.

Let's introduce a function to describe such demand, called memory pressure $M_{press}(l, t)$. Memory pressure depends on l – the tree level at which we consider memory pages – and time to capture the tree size dynamics over time. The reason for dependency on level is different demand for intermediate tree nodes and leaves. Since intermediate nodes have to be read into memory for more queries than leave nodes, the experience less memory pressure overall. An extreme case is the tree root node, which always stays in memory.

Having this function in place, we can describe the amount of I/O generated by Q queries as:

$$IO_{read}(t) = Q_{read} \cdot \sum_{l=1}^L M_{press}(l, t) \cdot \frac{N_l t}{N(t)} \quad (1)$$

Here $L(n)$ is the depth of the B-Tree, N_l is the number of pages at depth l .

To simplify the model, let's consider a global memory function instead, $M_{press}(t)$, which looks like this:

$$M_{press} = \begin{cases} \frac{N(t)-M}{N(t)}, & N > M \\ 0, & N < M \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In (2) memory pressure does not depend on the tree level anymore, we evaluate it for every page in the tree. On the other hand it depends on $N(t)$ – number of pages in the tree and M – the buffer cache size. In other words, the function says the more pages do not fit into the cache the more is memory pressure. This simplified version of memory pressure allows us to finalize the formula:

$$IO_{read}(t) = Q_{read} \cdot M_{press}(t) \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{N_l(t)}{N(t)} = Q_{read} \cdot M_{press}(t) \quad (3)$$

2.2.3 *Insert-only workload.* In the problem formalization section we have mentioned that the database is configured in such a way that reduces not relevant I/O operations as much as possible. But it's not possible to have B-Tree only operations, and even after stripping down everything we still got few types of I/O:

- The target buffer has to be present in the memory before modification. It means that, similarly to the read-only workload, the buffer has to be read from the disk if needed.
- A WAL record for the transaction commit has to be flushed to disk. Note, that it's not about a WAL record for the actual insert operation (to avoid this I/O we use an unlogged table) it's really only about committing a transaction, and there is no way to avoid this I/O. The only thing one can do is to turn *fsync* option off to avoid syncing WAL record, but it has to be written anyway.
- A B-Tree page is full and has to be split. In that case a new zeroed page has to be allocated and written out.

The first type is the same as for read-only workload, and will be modeled as such. The second one is more complicated, because WAL writing is the subject of merge optimization. Performing a single I/O operation to write out multiple WAL records at once is usually beneficial, hence PostgreSQL allows configuring frequency of WAL writing. Intuitively it's clear that the amount of I/O related to WAL depends on the frequency configuration (the longer waiting time is, the less writes have to be done) and on the "density" of insert queries (large intervals between queries reduces importance of the waiting time).

In this work we use reciprocal of w_d (corresponds to the value of *wal_writer_delay* configuration) and Q_w , with coefficients $a_w = 10^3$, $b_w = 10^2$ derived empirically by fitting the formula to the experimental data:

$$W_g(Q_w) = \frac{a_w}{(w_d - b_w) \cdot (Q_w + 1)}$$

This represents the intuitive idea that longer waiting leads to more WAL records merged into one, and more queries within the same waiting time interval leads again to more WAL records being merged.

The third type of I/O depends on the workload and the data structure. Under the assumption made so far (uniform workload distribution and I records per index page) we could simply model it as $\frac{Q_w}{I}$.

2.2.4 *Generalized model.* Assuming that the workload consists of types described above, the final model for the I/O is a sum of all the components:

$$IO(t) = Q \cdot M_{press}(t) + Q_w \cdot W_g(Q_w) + \frac{Q_w}{I} \quad (4)$$

2.3 Evaluation

To test properties of the model we have performed two series benchmarks: read-only and insert-only. The database and workload generators were configured in such ways that they could be compared with the model. The general setup looks like this:

- **PostgreSQL version:** We were using PostgreSQL 16 development version.

- **Workload:** PgBench was utilized to generate uniformly distributed read workload on a pre-populated and pre-warmed table.
- **The data schema:** We use a simple unlogged table (this allows to minimize amount of WAL written) with one integer column, and index on this column with the *fillfactor* 100 (this allows to simplify the way how we model the page structure). See Appendix for exact description of the schema.

For the read-only benchmark the most important details are:

- **Workload:** The initial data set was generated prior to the test. Before the test necessary prewarming was done to make sure the buffer cache is populated.
- **Output:** The result is amount of read I/O operations performed, which were collected via dynamic tracing of storage manager API. Similar aggregated information could be extracted using *pg_stat_io*, but using dynamic tracing allows us to get better resolution and numbers per relation. See the Appendix for more details about tracepoints used here.

The benchmark was done for different values of *shared_buffers*. The same parameters were chosen as input for the model, the Fig. 1 shows direct comparison. As expected:

- Lower amount of *shared_buffers* leads to higher number of I/O, since less data fits into the memory, and more pages have to be read from the disk.
- The amount of I/O goes down with the buffer cache size increasing, and hits the zero when everything could fit into the memory. After that the graph levels off.
- The model output closely follows the benchmark data. Let's define the relative error as an absolute difference between the model output and the benchmark data, normalized by the model value at every point. For the read-only workload the median of relative error is 0.4%, 95th percentile is 10% and the standard deviation is 5%. The largest error is concentrated at the turning point when everything fits into the memory.

Now lets consider the insert-only benchmark:

- **Workload:** PgBench was used to insert data in a retail fashion, one record at a time.
- **Output:** The result is amount of write I/O operations performed, which were collected via dynamic tracing of transaction manager API. See the Appendix for more details about tracepoints used here.

The benchmark was done for different values of *wal_writer_delay*. The same parameters were chosen as input for the model, the Fig. 2 shows direct comparison. As expected:

- Shorter *wal_writer_delay* leads to higher number of I/O, since less transaction commits are written together.
- The amount of I/O goes down in an exponential fashion with the WAL delay increasing, and hits the limit at the highest configurable delay value.
- The model output closely follows the benchmark data. As before, let's define the relative error as an absolute difference between the model output and the benchmark data,

Figure 1: Read I/O

Figure 2: Write I/O

normalized by the model value at every point. For the insert-only workload the median of relative error is 9%, 95th percentile is 16.5% and the standard deviation is 5.4%.

3 SIMULATING QUERY LATENCY

As we have mentioned in the previous section, it is hard to model query latency due to volatility and large number of factors impacting it. In this section we consider an alternative approach, when instead of exact modeling we will try to simulate query latency based on prior knowledge and empirical observations. While simple enough, this still allows us to derive some statistical properties for such metrics as query latency.

3.1 Formalization and limitations

A single database query interacting with a B-Tree could be thought of as a sequence of multiple simple steps, e.g. reading from and

writing to the network, updating a B-Tree page, committing the transaction etc. While still complex, those steps are generally more approachable for statistical analysis, allowing us to experimentally figure out how the latency distribution looks like for each of those steps. Having identified such smaller steps and their latencies we can simulate a database query as a state machine, which moves through various states and spends random amount of time in each state.

The first challenge is to identify into which steps to split a query. Let's call the amount of time it takes to perform a step its "size". In such terminology, those steps have to be "large" enough (i.e. take noticeable amount of time to perform) to make the whole simulation manageable, but "small" enough to feature simple latency distribution. To find the right balance we ran the expected workload (insert-only in a retail fashion, one record at a time) and profiled one PostgreSQL backend using *perf* throughout the run. Functions that were the largest contributors to the total set of samples formed the main steps.

The next challenge is to find a latency distribution for each of those steps. For that we ran the expected workload against PostgreSQL, augmented with two dynamic tracepoints firing at the enter and exit from the target function. BPF programs attached to the tracepoints were collecting execution latency. While introducing some overhead and impacting the final numbers, the assumption is that this approach does not change shape of the latency distribution. The implementation was using *bpffrace*, see Appendix for examples of used scripts.

3.2 Simulation

A single insert-only query is represented as a state machine with the following steps:

- **pq_getbyte**: Read from a network connection. The latency distribution was approximated by a two modal distribution $Pr(x_m = 10, \alpha = 1.4) + Normal(mean = 170, stddev = 40)$.
- **GetCachedPlan**: PgBench uses prepared transaction here, thus fetching a plan from the cache is needed. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 20, \alpha = 20)$.
- **btgettuple**: Get the next tuple in the index scan. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 20, \alpha = 10)$.
- **btinsert**: Insert an index tuple into a B-Tree. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 30, \alpha = 12)$.
- **heap_update**: Replace a tuple on a heap page. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 30, \alpha = 20)$.
- **heap_page_prune**: Opportunistically prune and repair fragmentation on a heap page. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 40, \alpha = 30)$.
- **CommitTransaction**: Commit the insert transaction. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 40, \alpha = 12)$.
- **socket_flush**: Flush output into a network connection. The latency distribution was approximated by $Pr(x_m = 40, \alpha = 20)$.

$Pr(x_m, \alpha)$ denotes a Pareto distribution with the scale parameter x_m and the shape parameter α . $Normal(mean, stddev)$ denotes a

Figure 3: pq_getbyte latency

Normal distribution with corresponding mean and standard deviation values. All the coefficients were chosen to approximate the experimental results. All the steps feature long tail latency distribution, with the **pq_getbyte** been especially long tailed and even multimodal, since we test without *fsync* and networking I/O turns out to be the most volatile. See Fig. 3 for an experimental data for latency distribution, where the red parts of the graph denote areas with most of the samples. The first red section contains approximately 90% of all samples and is the expected first mode. Somewhat surprisingly the second section accumulates on the total of about 10% of the samples, creating a second mode and contributing to the results.

The simulation itself consists of two core components: the simulation state and a simulation loop. The state is a priority heap, each element of which represent a timestamp in microseconds (us) and a current state of a simulated query. The loop iteration pops the earliest available step out of the state, samples the distribution attached to it and insert another element with the new accumulated timestamp and new step into the heap. Note that this simulation is quite simple and does not include e.g. an interaction between queries.

3.3 Evaluation

The expectations to get anything interesting out of such simulations were pretty low – after all simulated queries are not even interacting. To test properties of the simulation we have performed an insert-only benchmark, same as in the previous section. To reduce latency variance the testing machine was configured to not use Intel P-state, hyperthreads and performance scaling governor (see Appendix for more details). The resulting average query latency was 450us.

This result was compared with the output of simulation for 500 queries arriving at uniform intervals, larger than an average expected query latency (which is not very important in this particular context, as no contention is simulated). The resulting average queries latency was reported for each evaluation.

The first test was performed with a modified **pq_getbyte** latency distribution that did not have a second mode and such a long tail ($Pr(x_m = 10, \alpha = 10)$). The average query latency in this case was clearly lower than the real one, with the median of 300us. The second test was done with the real **pq_getbyte**, including the second mode and the long tail, as described above. To our surprise, with this change (to remind, that amounts to a small portion of all samples, about 10%) was causing the average latency to be 430us, which is much closer to the real numbers.

4 DERIVING STATISTICS ABOUT B-TREE BLOAT

The simplest way to build a model for pretty much anything based on experiments is to find patterns in the data. By extrapolating experimental data we could make reasonable predictions about dynamics of target metrics or aggregated statistics, which we could expect from them. As an example, in this section we will consider an important, but hard to estimate metric – number of dead tuples accumulated in a B-Tree.

4.1 Formalization

Due to how MVCC is implemented in PostgreSQL, tuples are not getting deleted right away [5]. They are marked as "dead" and remain present on a page until a vacuum operation cleans them up. B-Tree is not an exception, delete or modify operation leave dead tuples. Vacuuming of indexes is different from that of regular relations – unless specified via the option *INDEX_CLEANUP* vacuum will skip an index with not enough dead tuples. If such tuples are getting accumulated, it might cause index to become "bloated", requiring to perform more I/O than needed, thus it is important to be able to estimate how much bloat will be produced under a specified load.

We will consider two different metrics: amount of dead tuples per page, and overall amount of dead tuples in the index, as a cumulative result for all pages. For dead tuples at the index level we will rely on an extension **pgstattuple** [4], at the page we will use **pageinspect** [2].

4.2 Analysis

Lets consider the experimental data, produced by a simple update-only benchmark:

- **Workload:** PgBench was utilized to generate uniformly distributed update workload on a pre-populated and pre-warmed table.
- **The data schema:** As before, we use a simple unlogged table with one integer column, and index on this column with the *fillfactor* 100 (This allows to simplify the way how we model the page structure). See Appendix for exact description of the schema.
- **Metric:** Data was collected by periodically querying **pgstattuple** and **pageinspect**. See the definitions of queries in the Appendix.

The benchmark dimensions are number of dead tuples and time, the Fig. 4 shows results for a single B-Tree page. From this data we can draw following conclusions:

Figure 4: Dead tuples on a single page

Figure 5: Dead tuples in the index

- Despite the load producing dead tuples with every query, the runaway process of bloat accumulation is limited by micro-vacuuming [1].
- Essentially, every time when an index page is getting full, PostgreSQL tries to clean it up first, before doing an expensive page split. In this scenario, lots of tuples on the page are actually dead, thus cleaning is very efficient – in fact, under this load micro-vacuuming was enough to not cause any single page split.
- In long term number of dead tuples on a page behaves like an oscillator, periodically varying between zero and maximum possible number of tuples on a page.

Now let's have a look at what happens at the index level. Fig. 5 shows results for the whole B-Tree.

- Since index pages randomly receive updates, which are not correlated in any way, our expectations were to see a "white noise" on the dead tuples metric at the index level.

- Contrary to those expectations, the metric follows a similar pattern as a single page, showing a noticeable level of synchronization between various index pages.
- After a while number of dead tuples converges to about 20% of the whole data set, which is not far off from to usually reported utilization [12].

5 CONCLUSIONS

Databases intrinsic complexity makes tradition performance modeling challenging – it is simply hard to capture interaction of all moving components. One way to address that is to use "small" models, that predict behavior only of a certain database component in isolation. Such reductionist approach has its own advantages and downsides, which are discussed in this work alongside with the demonstration how it could be enhanced using metrics and event tracing to get new insights and make practical predictions.

The first example attempts to model an I/O profile for a B-Tree index, which is enhanced by static and dynamic tracing. The results are compared with benchmarking data and show convergence to the experimental numbers. The second example, enhanced with dynamic tracing to analyze execution latency, helps to get a grasp on query latencies. The results are also compared against and match close to the experimental data. The third example shows how simple metrics analysis can improve our understanding of internal database processes.

Such "small" models may have limited use on their own. But since they have clearly defined inputs and outputs, they could be combined with other models to provide more holistic picture. An example is the I/O profile of a B-Tree index, which is dealing with only a small subset of the whole I/O profile – for example it does not consider the filesystem cache at all. But this model could be combined with similar models for write ahead logging, checkpointing and filesystem cache [8] to build a full and comprehensive model.

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Appendices

A POSTGRESQL CONFIGURATION

To reduce amount of I/O to the bare minimum for modeling of B-Tree I/O profile, the following configuration was used:

- Disabled fsync operation (fsync = off). It introduces more I/O due to flushing data from memory to the durable storage and affect data durability.
- Disabled flushing WAL based on the amount of changes (wal_writer_flush_after = 0). Similarly to the fsync option, it produces more I/O due to flushing of the data.
- Same for checkpoint (checkpoint_flush_after = 0).
- Make checkpoint less frequent (checkpoint_timeout = 1d). Creating a checkpoint produces more I/O as well.
- Similar for the completion target (checkpoint_completion_target = 1.0).
- Increase the upper limit for WAL files (max_wal_size = 10GB).
- Disable autovacuum (autovacuum = off).

B TABLE SCHEMA AND QUERIES

In this section we specify which SQL queries were used for benchmarking.

B.1 Data schema

A very simple data schema was used throughout the testing, which contains a single table with a single column and an index on it.

```
create unlogged table test(a int);
create index on test(a)
with (fillfactor = 100);
```

B.2 Read-only load for B-Tree I/O profile

```
\set aid random(0, N)
-- a pre-populated table
select * from test where a = :aid;
```

B.3 Insert-only load for B-Tree I/O profile

```
\set aid random(0, N)
-- an empty table
insert into test values (:aid);
```

B.4 Update load for bloat estimation

```
\set aid random(0, 100000)
\set bid random(0, 100000)
-- a pre-populated table
update test_bloat set a = :aid
where a = :bid;
```

C PGBENCH OPTIONS

Since we use PgBench as a workload generator, its options are essential for testing:

- Fixed number of transactions to perform (-t). 10^4 for I/O profile, $2 \cdot 10^5$ for bloat and latency estimation.
- Fixed rate of transactions, or maximum (-rate). 10^3 for I/O profile, 500 for bloat and latency estimation.
- Since measurements are not concurrency sensitive, one client and one job (-c 1, -j 1)
- Reporting every 10 seconds (-P 10)
- Actual workload was specified via SQL file (-f workload.sql)

D TRACEPOINTS

To support model calibration we use following dynamic tracepoints:

D.1 Read I/O per relation and block

```
perf probe -x postgres --add
'smgrread reln->smgr_rlocator
.locator.relNumber:u32 blocknum:u32'

perf record -e probe_postgres:smgrread
--filter 'relNumber == ${REL_FILE_NODE}'
```

D.2 XLog write I/O

```
perf probe -x postgres XLogWrite:131
```

D.3 Micro-vacuuming

```
perf probe -x postgres --add
'_bt_simpledel_pass rel->rd_smgr->
smgr_rlocator.locator
.relNumber:u32 buffer:u32'
```

D.4 Function latency tracepoints

To support latency model calibration we utilize usual dynamic tracepoints (in the bpfttrace format), where the query step is a placeholder for one of described in the simulation part:

```
u:postgres:${QUERY_STEP}
uretprobe:postgres:${QUERY_STEP}
```

E NOISE REDUCING CONFIGURATION

Although we were trying to deal only with stable metrics, we used modified system configuration to reduce results variance:

```
cd /sys/devices/system/cpu/

# Disable turbo
echo 1 > intel_pstate/no_turbo

# Pin scaling governor
for i in cpu*/cpufreq/scaling_governor
do
    echo performance > $i
done
```

```
# Disable hyperthreading, where X
# represent the number of a CPU for
# a hyperthread
echo 0 > cpuX/online
```

F B-TREE BLOAT STATISTICS

Following queries were used to support bloat estimation:

```
SELECT dead_tuple_count
       FROM pgstattuple('test_bloat_a_idx');
SELECT dead_items
       FROM bt_page_stats('test_bloat_a_idx', 1);
```